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D6.5 - [Exploitation Strategy: Adaptation AGORA outcomes and results]

WP6 – [Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation]

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Partners short names / Legal name

APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
ATC	Athens Technology Center S.A.
BSC - CNS	Barcelona Supercomputing Center - Centro Nacional De Supercomputacion
FONDAZIONE CIMA	Centro Internazionale di Monitoraggio Ambientale – Fondazione CIMA
FONDAZIONE CMCC	Fondazione Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici
ECSA	Verein Der Europaeischen Buergerwissenschaften – ECSA E.v.
IBE	Fundación Ibercivis
ICLEI EURO	ICLEI European Secretariat GMBH (ICLEI EUROPASEKRETARIAT GMBH)
IIASA	Internationales Institut Fuer Angewandte Systemanalyse
SEI HQ	Stiftelsen The Stockholm Environment Institute
SEI OX	Stockholm Environment Institute, Oxford Office Limited
SEI TAL	Sihtasutus Stockholmi Keskkonnainstituudi Tallinna Keskus
UNIGE	Univeriste de Geneve

Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
ACH	Agora Community Hub
CA	Consortium Agreement
COP	UN Climate Change Conference
CoR	Committee of the Regions
D	Deliverable
DA	Digital Academy
EC	European Commission
ESA	European Space Agency
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
ICT	Information and Communication Tools
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KER	Key Exploitable Results
R&I	Research and Innovation
SERI	Swiss State Secretariate for Education, Research, and Innovation
TG	Target Group
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

The Adaptation AGORA exploitation plan outlines the strategy and methodology for managing innovation, Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), and ensuring the sustainability and legacy of the project results after the grant period concludes. The goal of this strategy is to drive actual, long-term transformational changes and implementations by establishing strategic collaborations with stakeholders like local institutions, municipal governance bodies, and local associations.

The exploitation strategy is a distinct effort from communication and dissemination activities, structured around two complementary processes: planning for impact before results are finalized (ex ante exploitation) and realizing that impact after results are achieved (ex post exploitation). While some activities, such as preliminary political inputs to pilot regions, have already begun, others will be implemented after the project ends.

To achieve its purpose, the plan details the knowledge and Intellectual Property (IP) emerging from Adaptation AGORA activities and defines an exploitation cascade based on three focus areas:

- **WHAT:** outlining the main exploitable assets/activities (Key Exploitable Results or KERs), their availability time, and the relevant target beneficiaries.
- **WHO:** identifying the specific target groups, and additional actors, that could benefit from or continue the project activities, supporting similar initiatives and increasing recognition.
- **HOW/WHAT FOR:** providing an outline of the exploitation and sustainability routes/roadmaps anticipated for each asset/activity during the project and beyond.

Following the introduction, this document details the exploitation plan and objectives (chapter 2) and provides a straightforward exploitation and sustainability roadmap (chapter 3). This roadmap outlines who will use the results (target groups) and what those results are. Next, the document covers the formal rules around project knowledge in intellectual property management (chapter 4), before briefly summarizing the past efforts in communication and dissemination activities (chapter 5). The entire document concludes by presenting the specific plans for making each result useful in the long term in exploitation plans per KER (chapter 6).

2. Exploitation plan and objectives

The uptake of the new knowledge generated in the project is designed to enable the acceleration of innovation actions in the context of climate adaptation, boosting the deployment of actions by securing attitudinal, managerial, and policy changes at regional, national and European levels and beyond. This is achieved through fine-tuned outreach strategies and co-creation processes. Adaptation AGORA results will impact the wider society, thanks to the active involvement of citizens whose expertise, perception, and experience participate in the shaping of climate adaptation solutions. Apart from the outputs produced in line with the Grant Agreement (GA), 7 KERs,

additional results have been collected (+5 KERs), indicating that many more could manifest even after the project end.

2.1. Main exploitation objectives

The overarching goal of the Adaptation AGORA exploitation strategy is to contribute to actual, long-term transformational changes and implementations by strategically collaborating with local institutions, municipal governance bodies, and regional task forces. This effort ensures the project's outputs are institutionalized and formally integrated into existing and future regional adaptation strategies, policy frameworks, and investment planning.

To achieve this primary goal, the exploitation strategy is driven by three core, strategic pillars:

Policy integration and institutionalization:

- Objective: to establish a formal, binding institutionalization of the co-produced local adaptation solutions, methodologies, and findings into the ongoing and future adaptation strategies, regulatory frameworks, and long-term investment cycles of the pilot cities/regions. This ensures the project's work is not a one-off study but a permanent fixture of local governance.

Replication and tool transfer:

- Objective: to establish a clear pathway for the rapid replication and large-scale deployment of the digital tools and the co-production methodology across the European Union (EU) Mission Adaptation ecosystem, ensuring these assets are adopted by the highest number of entities and integrated into other relevant Horizon Europe projects. This maximizes the value of the technical assets by measuring their adoption.

Long-Term digital sustainability and legacy:

- Objective: to secure a robust long-term hosting and maintenance model for the core digital assets after the project ends, ensuring they remain accessible and functional for example thanks to the hosting provided by platforms like weADAPT and Dataclime.

2.2. Specific exploitation plan objectives (operational steps)

The following specific objectives detailed the necessary steps the Adaptation AGORA Consortium had to undertake to establish and execute the exploitation plan:

- Determined a full set of the twelve KERs generated during the project;
- Established a clear roadmap for the exploitation of these results;
- Designated the IPR management methodology for all project outputs;
- Identified the primary target groups who would benefit from the KERs;
- Identified specific EU organisations that could benefit from the KERs;

- Defined strategies and actions needed to guarantee the application, continuation, replication, and scale-up of the project results.

3. Exploitation and sustainability roadmap

A four-step roadmap has been defined to achieve the project exploitation ambitions and objectives, and the project sustainability:

Step1: identification of the target groups.

Step2: identification of the KERs.

Step3: exploitation plans per KER and actions needed.

Step 4: sustainability opportunities.

3.1 Identification of the target groups

A preliminary total number of 8 target groups (TG) to which communication and dissemination activities are dedicated, were identified before the start of the project. Here below their division and related specifications:

TG1 - Local Communities: to engage citizens in an active role in climate adaptation, from design to implementation.

TG2 - Academia and Research (Registered Training Authorities, universities, schools, international civil society organisations, networks, experts): to share knowledge and expertise across disciplines, inform about the project results and outcomes and to strengthen existing climate adaptation platforms. This target group is now including also practitioners in the field of climate change and climate change adaptation strategies, as the applied research is directly integrated into the development of strategies and plans of private and public institutions, as well as local, regional and national frameworks.

TG3 - Governments and Decision-Makers (local and regional authorities for climate adaptation; policymakers at local, regional and EU levels; policy advisors, i.e. institutes and public agencies at local, regional and EU levels): to identify enablers and barriers to citizen engagement in climate adaptation, to enhance the understanding of local communities in climate adaptation and to learn to use the tools made available by the project.

TG4 - Civil Society (citizens, civil society organisations, NGOs, young associations): to maximise the citizens' empowerment through the project's activities, and tools. This target group is now including also multi-ethnic groups, which provide valuable input and knowledge from climate related hazards that may have impacted their geographical region of origin and are now impacting the city and/or region where they live. Furthermore, the civil society cohort also incorporated in some Pilots

“vulnerable communities”, where vulnerability in this case can be defined as the characteristics and circumstances of a community that make it susceptible to the damaging effects of a climate hazard.

TG5 - Citizens/Public Opinion: to raise awareness on climate adaptation, how to tackle disinformation, and enable citizen engagement in climate adaptation policy and actions

TG6 - Investors (local businesses, small, medium and large firms, financial institutions, publicly owned enterprises, institutional investors): to enhance engagement and awareness of the business sector in the climate adaptation strategies.

TG7 - Media (journalists, communications officers, publishers and digital media publishers, editors): to amplify the multi audience reach of the project, increase the visibility of the activities, enhance public awareness of climate adaptation and how to address disinformation.

TG8 - Consortium Partners and EC project officers - to ensure adequate and timely communication about the project’s steps and progress.

3.2 Identification of the KERs

The project initially identified seven preliminary KERs. This number later grew to twelve during the implementation phase, a direct result of positive feedback received from stakeholders and new ideas generated by the consortium.

Table 1: Overview of project KERs

KER (Key Exploitable Results with short description) [TG] [Work Package (WP)]
KER1 - Portfolio of initiatives, projects, platforms and solutions for local communities and stakeholder engagement to foster climate change adaptation [TG1 – Local Communities; TG2 – Academia and Research; TG3 – Governments and Decision-Makers; TG4 – Civil Society] [WP1, WP3, WP4, WP6].
KER2 - Landscape of communities and regions joining the Mission or to be involved in the transformative journey towards climate resilience [TG4 – Civil Society; TG5 – Citizens/Public Opinion] [WP1, WP2, WP6].
KER3 - Cross-sectoral frameworks for co-evaluating existing and innovative best practices for climate adaptation engaging key stakeholders [TG1 – Local Communities; TG4 – Civil Society; TG5 – Citizens/Public Opinion; TG6 – Investors] [WP3].
KER4 - Co-design and co-create innovative best practices for engaging key stakeholders [TG3 – Governments and Decision-Makers; TG4 – Civil Society; TG6 – Investors] [WP1, WP2, WP3, WP5].
KER5 - Adaptation AGORA ICT Tool (“Digital Agora”, including “Digital Academy to gather and analyse relevant data and monitor climate risks” and “Digital Academy against Climate Change Disinformation”) [TG1 – Local communities; TG2 – Academia and Research; TG3 – Governments and Decision-Makers; TG4 – Civil Society; TG7 – Media]. [WP3, WP5]. In Chapter 6, KER5 will be split in two: KER5-A and KER5-B.

<p>KER6 - Mobile app to counteract disinformation on Climate Change [TG4 – Civil Society; TG5 – Citizens/Public Opinion; TG7 – Media] [WP2].</p>
<p>KER7 - Climate Adaptation Citizen engagement digital handbook [TG1 – Local Communities; TG2 – Academia and Research; TG3 - Governments and Decision-Makers; TG4 – Civil Society; TG5 – Citizens/Public Opinion; TG6 – Investors; TG7 – Media; TG8 - Consortium Partners and EC project Officers] [WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6].</p>
<p>During the first year and a half of project, additional KERs were identified:</p>
<p>KER8 - Roadmap for transformational change [TG2 – Academia and Research; TG3 – Governments and Decision-Makers; TG6 – Investors; TG8 – Consortium Partners and EC project Officers] [WP4].</p>
<p>KER9 - Peer to peer learning activities [TG2 – Academia and Research; TG3 – Governments and Decision-Makers; TG5 – Citizens/Public Opinion] [WP2, WP5].</p>
<p>KER10 - Supporting strategic documents and policy impact in pilot regions and beyond [TG2 – Academia and Research; TG3 – Governments and Decision-Makers] [WP2, WP4].</p>
<p>KER11 - Network of international related projects and stakeholders [Scientific community; TG8 – Consortium Partners; TG7 – Media; TG3 – Governments and Decision-Makers; TG6 – Investors] [WP6].</p>
<p>KER12 - Adaptation AGORA online presence [All target audience] [WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6].</p>

4. Intellectual property management

Adaptation AGORA Consortium embraces the need to protect IP of the project’s assets in the context of the Adaptation AGORA exploitation strategy outside the project context, during the project’s life span as well as the Confidentiality period. In general, the key concepts to consider for designing the intellectual property management strategy of Horizon Europe projects are the following:

- Background and access rights to background;
- Ownership of results;
- Rights of use of the granting authority on materials, documents and information received for policy, information, communication, dissemination and publicity purposes.

Therefore, the following sub-chapters aim to clarify the main terms concerning the key elements of intellectual property management.

4.1 Grant Agreement Preparation State

Both the GA and the Consortium Agreement (CA) constitute documents which include a description of several issues related to Access Rights for background and project results on Fair and Reasonable conditions (*“Appropriate conditions, including possible financial terms or royalty-free conditions, taking into account the specific circumstances of the request for access, for example the actual or potential value of the results or background to which access is requested and/or the scope, duration or other characteristics of the exploitation envisaged”*). Their unique provisions represent a reference point for IPR issues among the project partners. In this respect, any further advancements regarding IPR actions to be put in place by project partners will be facilitated under the underlying provisions. During the implementation stage of the project, IPR handling procedures are foreseen to be applied among the Adaptation AGORA partners to properly realise results/assets management of the project. In this respect, as the project evolves, the focus will be on background and foreground identification, assets’ ownership, access rights, and protection, as well as the exploitation of the project’s results. The Adaptation AGORA IP management emphasises on establishing robust handling procedures that are of strategic importance to the project to facilitate the exploitation of its results.

4.2 Background and access rights to background

The beneficiaries must give each other, and the other participants, access to the background identified as needed for implementing the action, subject to any specific rules in Annex 5 of the GA. ‘Background’ means any data, know-how or information, whatever its form or nature (tangible or intangible), including any rights such as IPR, that is: (a) held by the beneficiaries before they acceded to the Agreement and (b) needed to implement the action or exploit the results. If background is subject to rights of a third party, the beneficiary concerned must ensure that it is able to comply with its obligations under the Agreement.

4.3 Ownership of results

The granting authority does not obtain ownership of the results produced under the action. ‘Results’ means any tangible or intangible effect of the action, such as data, know-how or information, whatever its form or nature, whether or not it can be protected, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights.

4.4 Rights of use of the granting authority

The granting authority's rights to use the materials, documents, and information received for policy, communication, dissemination, and publicity purposes are subject to a specific policy. The granting authority has the right to use non-sensitive information relating to the action and materials and documents received from the beneficiaries (notably summaries for publication, deliverables, as well as any other material, such as pictures or audio-visual material, in paper or electronic form) for

policy, information, communication, dissemination and publicity purposes, during the action or afterwards.

The right to use the beneficiaries' materials, documents and information is granted in the form of a royalty-free, non-exclusive and irrevocable licence, which includes the following rights:

(a) Use for its own purposes (in particular, making them available to persons working for the granting authority or any other EU service (including institutions, bodies, offices, agencies, etc.) or EU Member State institution or body; copying or reproducing them in whole or in part, in unlimited numbers; and communication through press information services).

(b) Distribution to the public (in particular, publication as hard copies and in electronic or digital format, publication on the internet, as a downloadable or non-downloadable file, broadcasting by any channel, public display or presentation, communicating through press information services, or inclusion in widely accessible databases or indexes).

(c) Editing or redrafting (including shortening, summarising, inserting other elements (e.g. meta-data, legends, other graphic, visual, audio or text elements), extracting parts (e.g. audio or video files), dividing into parts, use in a compilation).

(d) Translation.

(e) Storage in paper, electronic or other form.

(f) Archiving, in line with applicable document-management rules.

(g) The right to authorise third parties to act on its behalf or sub license to third parties the modes of use set out in Points (b), (c), (d) and (f), if needed for the information, communication and publicity activity of the granting authority.

(h) Processing, analysing, aggregating the materials, documents and information received and producing derivative works.

The rights of use are granted for the whole duration of the industrial or IPR concerned. If materials or documents are subject to moral rights or third-party rights (including IPR or rights of natural persons on their image and voice), the beneficiaries must ensure that they comply with their obligations under this Agreement (in particular, by obtaining the necessary licences and authorisations from the rights holders concerned). Where applicable, the granting authority will insert the following information:

"© – [year] – [name of the copyright owner]. All rights reserved. Licensed to the [name of granting authority] under conditions."

For the University of Geneva (UNIGE) partner in Switzerland, as the funding was received via a grant from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI), all project results must include the following disclaimer: "This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI)."

4.5 Specific rules on IPR, results and background

Specific rules regarding intellectual property rights, results and background are set out in Annex 5 of the GA.

4.6 Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this Article, the grant may be reduced (see Article 28 of the GA). Such a breach may also lead to other measures described in Chapter 5 of the GA.

5. Communication and dissemination activities in brief

The inclusion of brief summaries of communication (Chapter 5.1) and dissemination (Chapter 5.2) activities within the exploitation plan is essential to better understand this deliverable (D). The communication brief validates that the project has generated the necessary public and political awareness (e.g., through mass media and high-level forums) required to create demand and support for the KERs. Meanwhile, the dissemination brief proves that the KERs have achieved scientific credibility and pan-European replication potential by transferring methodologies to expert communities and integrating them into strategic networks (e.g., MIP4Adapt). Together, these sections confirm that the KERs are not only technically robust but have also been strategically positioned for successful adoption, making the detailed exploitation pathways outlined in the subsequent chapters achievable. Integrative information is available in D6.4, Dissemination and Communication Report.

5.1. Communication activities

The project's communication strategy was dedicated to generating widespread awareness and driving direct engagement across every major stakeholder group. It prioritized maximizing visibility through social media and mass media channels, such as the Italian RAI 1 TV show and local radio interviews, ensuring the project's visibility reached the broader public and generated essential interest derived from the pilot experiences. Communication served as the primary advocacy tool for political and institutional bodies, ensuring high-level awareness at forums such as the 30th session of the United Nations Climate Change Conference, referred to as COP30 (Belém, Brazil) and the United Nations University ICEGOV 2025 Conference (Abuja, Nigeria), which promoted the project's digital tools for governance. This institutional reach was supported by advocacy efforts including the Global Symposium on Climate Justice and Impacted Populations (Brazil) and outreach to regional policy-makers via the Baltic Sea Regional Forum (Estonia) and the research and innovation (R&I) for a competitive green transition (Brussels) event. Furthermore, the strategy created vital links to the private sector and specialized bodies: focused peer-learning workshops on "Heat resilience in healthcare" targeted specific professional groups, while direct engagement with corporate resilience leaders such as in ACCIONA WAT showcased the Digital Tools for immediate

business application. This multi-pronged communication approach ensured that awareness was built across all sectors necessary for later exploitation.

Figure 1. Baltic Sea Regional Forum for the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change, Estonia, 2025. Credits: MIP4adapt.

5.2. Dissemination activities

The Dissemination strategy focused on transferring validated methodologies and technical knowledge to peer researchers, experts, and technical practitioners who could utilize and further develop the KERs. This ensured the objective of Pan-European replication and tool transfer was met. The project was presented for academic and expert validation to specialized communities like the SISC (climate science) to validate and disseminate the specific engagement processes and pilot results, establishing them as authoritative scientific assets.

This effort was further reinforced by key contributions to international scientific events, including the ESA Living Planet Symposium 2025 and the high-level Adaptation Futures 2025 conference, ensuring the project's methodologies were scrutinized and shared within the highest echelons of remote sensing and global climate research communities. Crucially, Mission cross-pollination was achieved through dedicated strategic exchanges with MIP4Adapt and with the EU Mission Adaptation Community. These events focused strictly on transferring methodologies and results to other EU Mission projects and experts, ensuring the rapid uptake and scalability of Adaptation AGORA's KERs across the European R&I ecosystem.

6. Exploitation plans per KER

The Adaptation AGORA project generated a comprehensive set of KERs designed to foster long-term transformational change and enhance climate change adaptation across Europe. This suite of resources is structured to ensure maximum accessibility and impact, extending from interactive digital platforms and capacity-building resources to policy instruments and extensive collaborative networks. The project's strategy centers on empowering diverse stakeholders, including local communities, governments, civil society, and academia, by providing validated tools and knowledge to address climate risks and disinformation. These KERs collectively represent the lasting legacy of Adaptation AGORA, offering concrete support and strategic guidance for climate adaptation well beyond the project's lifetime, ensuring that the knowledge and methodologies developed are easily accessible and replicable across the continent and beyond.

6.1. Digital assets and their sustainability

Adaptation AGORA developed four key digital tools: the [Agora Community Hub](#) (ACH), two Digital Academies ([Climate Change Disinformation](#) & [Climate data Risks and Tools](#)), a mobile app (available on [Google Play](#) & [App Store](#)), and a [digital handbook](#).

- The ACH serves as a core exploitation outcome, built as a microsite of the long-term supported weADAPT platform (developed by SEI). This guarantees continuous visibility of Adaptation AGORA content at the regional, national, EU, and across the continent and beyond.
- Similarly, the two Academies (Climate Change Disinformation & Climate data Risks and Tools), and the digital handbook, will remain accessible and operational beyond the project's duration. The Academy on the use of climate data is hosted by [Dataclime](#), a platform owned by CMCC, which will ensure a long-lasting availability and legacy of project results. The Academy on Climate Change Disinformation is hosted on ATC's servers and will remain accessible for at least 3 years after the end of the project. ATC plans to keep the academy online beyond the 3 years milestone, as one of ATC's assets and will seek to secure funding to actively maintain the digital academy (DA) for 5-10 years so that its content (modules, fact-checks, resources) remains up to date and available in other languages and/or modalities.
- The Mobile App, developed by IBERCIVIS, will continue to be accessible and used, and has been created in an open access format, with the full code being available in GitHub, so that other projects can potentially use it, improve it, and even adapt it in other languages. By discussing this digital tool with decision makers in various regions, there is a high interest in developing further the App or creating adapted versions based on this initial corner stone.

This sustainability is central to Adaptation AGORA's mission to disseminate valuable climate change data knowledge, combat disinformation, and ensure the project's key takeaways remain available.

Because of this, it has also been considered how the tools interact with one another, the target audiences that each of them is able to reach, as well as the information and key data they hold.

As the project website replicates information that can be mirrored in the Information and Communication Tools (ICTs) which are going to continue after the lifecycle of the project, the reports, outputs and deliverables will also be available in the ACH and in the Digital Handbook. Likewise, they will be available in the [Zenodo Community](#), expanding the outreach and ensuring that when the existing contract and domain for the adaptation agora website expires, all the key results from the project will continue to be available.

6.2. Strategic amplification and policy Impact

A core element of the exploitation strategy is the active amplification and strategic knowledge transfer through high-impact events and collaborations. This includes synergies with other projects, local authorities, and stakeholders joining Pilot workshops and webinars. The project strategically leverages major international forums to secure the exploitation of its results and policy recommendations. For instance, by presenting at the [Living Planet Symposium 2025](#) (organized by the European Space Agency, ESA), Adaptation AGORA ensures its citizen engagement methodologies are positioned within the Earth Observation community.

Similarly, contributions to high-level policy events, such as [Adaptation Futures 2025](#) (New Zealand) and [COP30](#) (Brazil), guarantee the project's policy findings are formally introduced at the forefront of global climate change negotiations, maximizing the uptake and implementation of recommendations for real-world impact.

The exploitation plan foresees the continuity of the results from the project, together with an additional set of international and local events where the outputs will be shared with key stakeholders. The full details of the dissemination events are included in D6.4 yet it is worth noting that the exploitation potential of the results from this project can be expanded based on these activities. For instance, members of the project have been invited to co-chair European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) 2026's session "Co-Created Citizen Science for Transformative Environmental and Sustainable Futures", where new ways in which Adaptation AGORA's results are exploited can be evidenced.

6.3. Key exploitable results roadmap

Here below the roadmaps associated with each of the twelve identified KERs.

KER1	
<p>© Viktor Talashuk, Unsplash.</p>	<p>Portfolio of initiatives, projects, platforms and solutions for local communities and stakeholder engagement to foster climate change adaptation.</p>
<p>Main contributors to the KER</p>	<p>BSC; SEI-OX, IBERCIVIS, ATC, CIMA, UNIGE, CMCC.</p>
<p>IP background</p>	<p>No IP background for KER identified</p>
<p>KER owner</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Expected benefits from exploiting the KER</p>	<p>Knowledge sharing. WP1 mapping of citizens engagement initiatives for climate adaptation, and capacity building resources on climate change adaptation and disinformation campaigns could support knowledge development and sharing in several TGs. Moreover, WP4 provides an overview of barriers and enablers to citizen engagement. The initiatives include: 1) Learning from, and being inspired by, the experiences of others; and 2) Identifying and locating tools and techniques relevant to citizen involvement in climate adaptation action; 3) Provide insides to overcome barriers and leverage on enablers.</p>
<p>Target groups</p>	<p>TG1 - Local Communities; TG2 - Academia and Research; TG3 - Governments and Decision-Makers; TG4 - Civil Society.</p>
<p>Specific EU organisations that could benefit from the KER</p>	<p>European Committee of the Regions (CoR) / Policy Learning Platform (Interreg Europe), European Social Fund Plus (ESF+) Managing Authorities (for social innovation in adaptation), European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA) (for assessing inclusivity of solutions), European Network for Rural Development (ENRD) (for solutions relevant to rural and farming communities), EU Regional Innovation Smart Specialisation Strategies (RIS3) Platforms, European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities (ALLEA) (for evidence-based solution vetting), European Association of Development Agencies (EURADA), Platform for Coal Regions in Transition (for diversification solutions), European Association for Local Democracy (ALDA).</p>

Exploitation pathway	An online repository accessible via the ACH, tailored to practitioners, civil society and interested local communities.
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KER2	
<p>© MIP4Adapt.</p>	<p>Landscape of communities and regions joining the Mission or to be involved in the transformative journey towards climate resilience. The Mission aims to engage diverse regions and communities, supporting them in their climate adaptation journey, regardless of their starting point.</p>
Main contributors to the KER	CMCC; CIMA; ECSA; APRE
IP background	No IP background for KER identified
KER owner	N/A
Expected benefits from exploiting the KER	<p>Upscaling. Adaptation AGORA facilitated the participation of regional and local authorities in the Mission, focusing on followers and pilots, enabling them to collaborate, secure resources, and implement adaptation activities tailored to their specific needs. For this purpose, two webinars on citizen science were organized in collaboration with the Mission Implementation Platform, during which the participants were guided into proven methods for effective stakeholder and citizen engagement in climate adaptation. Additionally, citizen-driven soft adaptation measures were presented at the Baltic Sea Regional Forum, there Adaptation AGORA engaged with policy-makers and cities and helped translate concrete local practices into practical strategies that support institutional uptake and local adaptation planning. These exchanges promote cross-regional learning and enable regions to integrate proven participatory methods into their own heat-risk strategies.</p>
Target groups	TG4 - Civil Society; TG5 - Citizens/Public Opinion.
Specific EU organisations that could benefit from the KER	<p>Interreg Baltic Sea Region, net4Society (or equivalent Horizon Europe National Contact Point Networks), ERA-NETs and Joint Programming Initiatives (JPIs) on Climate, European Climate Research Alliance (ECRA), European Environment Agency (EEA), European Topic Centre on Climate Change Adaptation (ETC CA), European Commission (DG CLIMA and DG REGIO), EU Joint Research Centre (JRC), EU Mission Implementation Platform for Adaptation to Climate Change (MIP4Adapt), Climate-ADAPT, Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy.</p>

Exploitation pathway	By facilitating the stakeholders in joining the Mission's activities or other climate-related initiatives, guiding them through steps and possibilities. By sharing these initiatives with the project pilot regions and followers, which in most cases have been decision-makers.
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KER3	
<p>© Scott Graham, Unsplash.</p>	<p>Cross-sectoral frameworks for co-evaluating existing and innovative best practices for climate adaptation engaging key stakeholders. Cross-sectoral frameworks provide a structured approach to co-evaluate existing and innovative best practices for climate adaptation, ensuring a comprehensive and integrated response.</p>
Main contributors to the KER	UNIGE; IIASA; SEI-OX; SEI HQ; ECSA; IBERCIVIS; CMCC; BSC.
IP background	No IP background for KER identified
KER owner	N/A
Expected benefits from exploiting the KER	<p>Cross-sectoral frameworks offer a multitude of advantages for co-evaluating climate adaptation best practices. Here are some key benefits:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing knowledge (including learning from mistakes); • Improving decision-making; • Increasing interdisciplinary collaboration; • Increasing public trust and support; • Fostering inclusion of lower represented categories.
Target groups	TG1 - Local Communities; TG4 - Civil Society; TG5 - Citizens/Public Opinion; TG6 – Investors.
Specific EU organisations that could benefit from the KER	European Environment Agency (EEA), European Topic Centre on Climate Change Adaptation (ETC CA), European Commission (DG CLIMA and DG REGIO), EU Joint Research Centre (JRC), EU Mission Implementation Platform for Adaptation to Climate Change (MIP4Adapt), Climate-ADAPT, Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy, ICLEI - Local Governments for Sustainability.
Exploitation pathway	The exploitation pathway for the cross-sectoral evaluation framework focuses on validation through real-world application before ensuring its long-term accessibility. This strategy guarantees the framework is robust, user-friendly, and credible across diverse sectors. The Adaptation AGORA

website and the weADAPT platform could facilitate the process furnishing learning and exchange opportunities.

<p>KER4</p>	
<p>© Adaptation AGORA</p>	<p>Co-design and co-create innovative best practices for engaging key stakeholders, and long-term capacity building. With focus on the Pilot activities and on the analysis of best practices for citizen engagement (D1.2), this KER aims at exploiting the structure of the co-creation workshops into a manual of best practices.</p>
<p>Main contributors to the KER</p>	<p>SEI-OX; SEI HQ; ECSA; IBERCIVIS; CMCC; APRE; ICLEI; BSC.</p>
<p>IP background</p>	<p>No IP background for KERs identified</p>
<p>KER owner</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Expected benefits from exploiting the KER</p>	<p>Inspire new frontiers in citizen engagement. Stakeholder engagement is a critical aspect of any project or initiative and involves several steps, from mapping to action. Adaptation AGORA could support upcoming projects and initiatives by furnishing a manual of best practices in stakeholder engagement and co-design workshops, made of examples based on the Pilot activities and co-design of the ACH, fine-tuned for each stakeholder group. Strengthen science-policy collaboration. Continued collaboration is expected to build trust and foster co-exploration and co-creation processes that support local ownership, local relevance, research/knowledge uptake, awareness-raising, as well as more informed decision-making. For example, key stakeholders in the Swedish pilot have demonstrated an improved understanding of urban heat vulnerability and adaptation.</p>
<p>Target groups</p>	<p>TG3 – Governments and Decision-Makers; TG4 - Civil Society; TG6 – Investors.</p>
<p>Specific EU organisations that could benefit from the KER</p>	<p>European Association for Public Administration Accreditation (EAPAA) (for certifying public engagement processes), European Academy of Participation (EAP), European Youth Information and Counselling Agency (ERYICA) (for youth capacity building tools), European Centre of Expertise in the field of Local Government (CECLG) (Council of Europe), Association of Schools of Political Studies (Council of Europe), European Network for Innovation in Public Administration (EIPA), and ECSA.</p>

<p>Exploitation pathway</p>	<p>Report and guidelines made of workshop briefs divided into stakeholder groups, available on the Adaptation AGORA website. Moreover, information was shared with followers and other stakeholders, and many additional events were organised to further expand the impact of the project and capitalise on its results by replicating its methodologies in different contexts.</p>
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<p>KER5-A</p>	
<p>© Adaptation AGORA</p>	<p>Agora Community Hub. It is the living digital environment that enables users to network and learn, facilitating them to find resources such as case studies, and peers and communities from other geographical or societal contexts to share challenges and needs.</p>
<p>Main contributors to the KER</p>	<p>SEI-OX; CMCC; APRE; ICLEI.</p>
<p>IP background</p>	<p>No IP background for KERs identified</p>
<p>KER owner</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Expected benefits from exploiting the KER</p>	<p>Fostering collaboration. The Hub provides information and knowledge for local government, municipal services, and communities. Resources enclose local to municipal level tools and approaches, including case studies and stories sharing experience (enablers, barriers, and lessons learned). As a microsite of the weADAPT platform, a “leading collaborative platform for climate change adaptation”, with themes on the ACH such as “Heat Resilience and Health”, co-developed with the Dresden pilot, and connected to the themes on weADAPT such as “Youth, Justice and Education” the ACH maximizes networking opportunities and links with other projects and initiatives that will be using these themes e.g. the Horizon Europe Innovation Action, Directed which will be hosting a Climate Youth Festival in early 2026 in Hungary, where the ACH will be shared and promoted. These initiatives will continue to expand the reach of the ACH among different citizen groups across Europe.</p>
<p>Target groups</p>	<p>TG1 – Local communities; TG2 – Academia and Research; TG3 – Governments and Decision-Makers; TG4-Civil Society; TG7-Media.</p>
<p>Specific EU organisations that could benefit from the KER</p>	<p>European Climate Pact, European Committee of the Regions (CoR)/RegHub Network, European Network of Regional and Local Authorities for Sustainable Development (RESILIENT REGIONS), European Association for Local Democracy (ALDA),</p>

	European Environmental Bureau (EEB), European Digital Platform for Citizen Science (or similar citizen science networks), EURODESK (for connecting youth and local stakeholders), The European Students' Union (ESU), European University Association (EUA), European Association of Geosciences and Remote Sensing Students (AAGRS), European Student Think Tank (ESTT)
Exploitation pathway	Hosted as a microsite on the weADAPT platform after the project has finished, providing access to project results to a wide community and creating long term legacy.

KER5-B & KER5-C	
<p>© Adaptation AGORA</p>	Adaptation AGORA provides two Digital Academies (“To access and use Climate Data and monitor Climate Risk”KER 5-C, and “Against Climate Change Disinformation” KER5-B) to support citizens and stakeholders to access open-source climate data.
Main contributors to the KER	Platform development: CMCC; ATC Modules and content development: CMCC, ATC, IIASA; IBERCIVIS, APRE, CIMA, UNIGE, SEI Tallinn.
IP background	No IP background for KERs identified
KER owner	ATC (DA against Climate Change Disinformation) CMCC (Climate Data Risk & Tools Academy)
Expected benefits from exploiting the KER	<p>Data quality and accessibility. Adaptation AGORA's academies can contribute to increasing public awareness of climate-related issues and adaptation strategies and serve as a foundation for decision-making and climate-risk monitoring processes.</p> <p>The Academies also offer guidance on data interpretation and its effective use. For example, the DA against Climate Change Disinformation provides reliable information on climate change, motivating readers in developing critical thinking in the identification of fake news. Based on scientific evidence, it identifies and debunks common climate change myths and equips citizens with the tools to counter misinformation.</p> <p>These tools can further be exploited by the two institutions that developed the ICTs by incorporating them into new</p>

	Horizon Europe or other projects targeting citizen engagement and empowerment.
Target groups	TG1 – Local communities; TG2 – Academia and Research; TG3 – Governments and Decision-Makers; TG4-Civil Society; TG7-Media.
Specific EU organisations that could benefit from the KER	European Training Foundation (ETF), European University Continuing Education Network (EUCEN), European Journalism Centre (EJC)/ European Federation of Journalists (EFJ) (for the disinformation module), EIT Climate-KIC (for climate innovation training), European Public Health Alliance (EPHA) (for health data literacy), European Schoolnet (EUN) (for teacher training resources), EUROSTAT (for promoting data literacy/usage), European Centre of Excellence for Countering Hybrid Threats (Hybrid CoE) (for disinformation training), European Association for the Education of Adults (EAEA), European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) (for digital security/data handling aspects)
Exploitation pathway	<p>Available through the Adaptation AGORA website and through the ACH. The Academy on the use of climate data is hosted by Dataclime, a platform owned by CMCC, which will ensure a long-lasting availability and legacy of project results. This academy has been integrated in project proposals, and it is expected that it will constitute the baseline for citizen empowerment.</p> <p>The Academy on Climate Change Disinformation is hosted on ATC’s servers and will remain accessible for at least 3 years after the end of the project and will seek to secure funding to actively maintain the DA for 5-10 years so that its content (modules, fact-checks, resources) remains up to date and available in other languages and/or modalities.</p> <p>In addition, ATC plans to enhance the DA with additional decision support features also leveraging ATC’s strong expertise in the development of specialized software for the media sector and in AI-supported claim/fake news/hate speech detection. ATC will integrate the DA in its media sector-oriented suite, a toolbox that allows users to access, retrieve, organize and analyse data sources and information pieces providing users with training modules and material around media literacy and disinformation (climate change and beyond).</p>

<p>KER6</p>	
<p>© Adaptation AGORA</p>	<p>Mobile app to counteract disinformation on Climate Change. “AGORA Quiz” is an educational mobile app designed to raise awareness about climate change and disinformation through an engaging quiz format. Developed within the Adaptation AGORA project, the app offers a fun, interactive way to enhance your knowledge on critical topics related to climate science, media literacy, and communication.</p>
<p>Main contributors to the KER</p>	<p>ATC; CMCC; ECSA; IBERCIVIS; APRE; IIASA.</p>
<p>IP background</p>	<p>No IP background for KERs identified</p>
<p>KER owner</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Expected benefits from exploiting the KER</p>	<p>Promotion of self-learning. The gamified mobile app aims to support the education of citizens on climate change adaptation and counter disinformation campaigns through an entertaining and engaging approach. By incorporating interactive elements, such as a scoreboard or ranking, the app transforms learning into an interactive and fun experience, encouraging engagement and active participation from stakeholders. This increases the engagement of citizens and other relevant groups in educating themselves and encourage their peers to follow suit. With the resources of the Adaptation AGORA project climate change disinformation is tackled and stakeholders are able to adopt sustainable behavioural patterns for climate adaptation.</p>
<p>Target groups</p>	<p>TG4 – Civil Society; TG5 - Citizens/Public Opinion; TG7 – Media.</p>
<p>Specific EU organisations that could benefit from the KER</p>	<p>European Youth Forum (YFJ), European Schoolnet (EUN), Erasmus+, EU Climate Pact Ambassadors (Youth Network), Youth and Environment Europe (YEE), The EU Science Hub (Joint Research Centre - JRC), Digital Competence Centres/Libraries, EURODESK, The European Students' Union (ESU).</p>
<p>Exploitation pathway</p>	<p>The app is available for download from mobile apps such as Play Store and Apple Store, and it is developed for both Android and iOS using agile methodologies. The app has been shared with followers and other communities so they can be used by all decision-makers in Europe.</p> <p>The Agora Quiz app will be also linked to other Ibercivis projects under the *Mission EU Adaptation JustSAFE *for the creation of new serious games focused on climate change</p>

education, the app will continue increasing its number of downloads through its integration and use in these initiatives.

In addition, it will keep being disseminated at key events, such as the upcoming *ECSA 2026* conference, strengthening opportunities for visibility, collaboration, and connections with other European communities and projects.

Online dissemination will also continue via partners' social media channels (e.g., Ibercivis and ECSA) and ECSA's newsletter (≈2,500 subscribers), among others.

These actions will continue to boost and maximize the app's downloads, expanding its reach among different citizen groups across Europe beyond the duration of the project.

KER7	
<p>© Adaptation AGORA</p>	<p>Digital handbook. "Voices of Climate Adaptation" hub is a critical knowledge asset that aims to translate complex adaptation science into relatable, actionable narratives. Its high-value lies in its capacity to serve as a peer-to-peer learning platform and an evidence repository for inclusive policy-making.</p>
Main contributors to the KER	CMCC; IBERCIVIS; SEI HQ; SEI-OX; SEI Tallin; ECSA
IP background	No IP background for KERs identified
KER owner	N/A
Expected benefits from exploiting the KER	Promotion of lessons learned. Being one of the final products of the project, the digital handbook will focus on sharing the experiences from the project, main topics discussed, and outcomes achieved, through a dynamic and user-friendly navigation system. Due to its nature, it will inspire stakeholders offering a set of information that could shape future projects and initiatives in the context of climate adaptation and citizen engagement.
Target groups	TG1 – Local Communities; TG2 – Academia and Research; TG3 – Governments and Decision-Makers; TG4 – Civil Society; TG5 – Citizens/Public Opinion; TG6 – Investors; TG7 – Media; TG8 – Consortium Partners and EC project Officers.
Specific EU organisations that could benefit from the KER	European Youth Forum (YFJ), European Schoolnet (EUN), Climate Outreach, European Environmental Bureau (EEB), Friends of the Earth Europe, C40 Cities Climate Leadership

	Group, European Civil Society Platform on Climate Adaptation (via thematic networks), ECOLISE (European Network for Community-Led Initiatives on Climate Change and Sustainability), Resilient Cities Network, Climate Alliance (Klima-Bündnis), C40 Cities Climate Leadership Group.
Exploitation pathway	Hosted by Dataclime, and accessible from the Adaptation AGORA website and the ACH. The handbook will be also promoted through external platforms, like Futurium.

KER8	
<p>© Adaptation AGORA</p>	<p>Roadmap for transformational change. The roadmap is a policy white paper highlighting strategic actions and governance mechanisms/structures that can support the upscaling of co-production/citizen engagement processes for climate resilience in Europe. The document provides sixteen recommendations structured around four key pillars: institutionalising engagement; strengthening local capacity; empowering citizens and stakeholders and sharing and applying knowledge and best practices. The recommendations are the culmination of invaluable contributions from Adaptation AGORA's extensive network.</p>
Main contributors to the KER	UNIGE; IIASA; CMCC, ICLEI; SEI-OX; ECSA
IP background	No IP background for KERs identified
KER owner	N/A
Expected benefits from exploiting the KER	The policy white paper will provide recommendations for the establishment of innovative and lasting governance mechanisms at regional, national and European scale that will support policymakers in the wide-scale implementation of co-production processes. It is poised to become a resource for decision-makers, offering a clear pathway to align European efforts with the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change.
Target groups	TG2 – Academia and Research; TG3 – Governments and Decision-Makers; TG6 – Investors; TG8 – Consortium Partners and EC project Officers.
Specific EU organisations that could benefit from the KER	European Parliament's Committee on the Environment, Public Health and Food Safety (ENVI), European Commission's Secretariat-General (SG)/Policy Labs, Committee of the Regions (CoR)/ENVE Commission, European Environment Agency (EEA)/European Topic Centre on Climate Change Adaptation (ETC CA), EU Mission Implementation Platform

	for Adaptation to Climate Change (MIP4Adapt), European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)/European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF) Management Authorities, Council of European Municipalities and Regions (CEMR), The European Political Strategy Centre (EPSC)/Think Tanks like Bruegel or CEPS, European Union National Institutes for Culture (EUNIC)/Culture & Climate Networks, Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy.
Exploitation pathway	Accessible from the Adaptation AGORA website, the ACH and the Horizon Results Portal . Disseminated through Adaptation AGORA and Mission Adaptation networks.

KER9	
<p>© Adaptation AGORA</p>	<p>Peer-to-Peer learning activities. A series of four Peer-to-Peer sessions has been planned to allow cross-fertilization between the Adaptation AGORA pilots and the Adaptation AGORA followers.</p>
Main contributors to the KER	CMCC; ICLEI; APRE; IBERCIVIS; SEI HQ; ECSA
IP background	No IP background for KERs identified
KER owner	N/A
Expected benefits from exploiting the KER	Co-explore adaptation strategies and experiences. Adaptation AGORA pilot activities collect valuable knowledge that can benefit other cities and regions. The dialogues that originated from the sessions aimed to provide a space for local governments and practitioners from different contexts to share insights, challenges, and solutions related to adaptation actions.
Target groups	TG2 – Academia and Research; TG3 – Governments and Decision-Makers; TG5 – Citizens/Public Opinion.
Specific EU organisations that could benefit from the KER	Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy, ICLEI - Local Governments for Sustainability, EUROCITIES, Committee of the Regions (CoR), Interreg Programmes (e.g., specific regional or transnational secretariats), European Union National Institutes for Culture (EUNIC)/Culture & Climate Networks, Council of European Municipalities and Regions (CEMR), European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) Management Authorities (for knowledge sharing mandates),

	European Topic Centre on Climate Change Adaptation (ETC CA).
Intended exploitation pathway	By sharing good practices on the ACH, by sharing insides on the Adaptation AGORA website, by sharing them in MIP4Adapt webinars, or events organised by other European funded projects.

KER10	
<p>© Adaptation AGORA</p>	Supporting strategic documents and policy impact in pilot regions and beyond.
Main contributors to the KER	CMCC; SEI HQ; ECSA; IBERCIVIS; UNIGE
IP background	No IP background for KERs identified
KER owner	N/A
Expected benefits from exploiting the KER	<p>Policy impact. Adaptation AGORA findings were presented in key strategic documents in different Pilot regions. In the Swedish Pilot, Adaptation AGORA findings successfully influenced policy and practice. Building on this momentum, the collaboration with the municipality of Malmö is continuing through the HeatSafe project, which directly mitigates heatwave vulnerabilities (https://www.sei.org/projects/heatsafe-mitigating-vulnerabilities-to-heatwaves-in-malmo/). Furthermore, the robust Adaptation AGORA evaluation framework is now being refined and tested for pan-European replication in other contexts, such as the FairWater project (https://www.sei.org/projects/fairwater/). A similar contribution was given by the Italian Pilot in the Climate Adaptation Strategy of Roma Capitale. In the future, CMCC will support the monitoring of the adaptation strategy implementation of the city of Rome. Such collaborations could facilitate decision making at different scales (cities, regions, nations, and at international level). Moreover, extensive reviews of policy instruments to support citizen engagement have been conducted, including lessons learnt from other sectors. These catalogues can provide useful insights also for other Member States and regions. Furthermore, Adaptation AGORA played a crucial role as a digital solution provider within the broader framework of the</p>

	EU Mission Adaptation to Climate Change. Its primary contribution was the establishment of the ACH, a platform designed as a digital meeting point for Regional and Local Authorities (ARLs) and citizens, facilitating the exchange of needs, knowledge, and practical adaptation experiences. Specifically, through tools like the Agora Explorer Map and discussion forums, the project demonstrated how digital platforms can be used to reduce the duplication of efforts and ensure that co-creation methodologies and pilot results are accessible and replicable across Europe, thereby contributing to the long-term sustainability of the Mission's outputs.
Target groups	TG2 – Academia and Research; TG3 – Governments and Decision-Makers.
Specific EU organisations that could benefit from the KER	Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy (CoM), Eurocities, ICLEI, European Environment Agency (EEA), Climate-KIC, European Citizen Science Association (ECSA), Climate Alliance (Klima-Bündnis), European Regions Research and Innovation Network (ERRIN), Joint Programming Initiative Climate (JPI Climate), European Environment Agency (EEA), European Committee of the Regions (CoR), Adaptation Futures (Conference Network).
Exploitation pathway	By sharing good practices on the ACH and by sharing insights on the Adaptation AGORA website. Also supporting specific requests from followers of the project, providing dedicated consultancy in terms of stakeholder engagement methodologies and processes, as done for the Italian follower Friuli Venezia Giulia Region.

KER11	
<p>© Adaptation AGORA</p>	Network of related international projects and stakeholders. Synergies with other projects and relevant stakeholders are foreseen to efficiently exploit the Adaptation AGORA results.
Main contributors to the KER	All partners
IP background	No IP background for KERs identified
KER owner	N/A

<p>Expected benefits from exploiting the KER</p>	<p>Fostering collaboration and giving a future prospective to the project. In relation to this topic, two main events saw the participation of Adaptation. The EGU 2025 session “Engaging Citizens in Understanding Urban Climate and Climate Change Risks through Participatory Science” will share the knowledge and experience acquired by Adaptation AGORA with the scientific community. The event “Citizens Together for Climate Adaptation”, that the team organized during the ECCA 2025, was an excellent opportunity to meet different communities in the fields of climate change adaptation and resilience, biodiversity, and societal transformation. The recurrent event (ECCA) is designed to involve many other European projects and initiatives, boosting their reach. Other collaborations and synergies such as with MAIA, I-CHANGE, CLIMAS, and MIP4ADAPT, happened on a periodic basis, and in some cases in the form of thematic working groups. The thematic working group with MIP4ADAPT, co-organized an event in 2025 on Behavioural Change for the Effectiveness of Policy Measures.</p>
<p>Target groups</p>	<p>Scientific community; TG8 – Consortium Partners; TG7 – Media; TG3 – Governments and Decision-Makers; TG6 – Investors.</p>
<p>Specific EU organisations that could benefit from the KER</p>	<p>EU Mission Implementation Platform for Adaptation to Climate Change (MIP4Adapt), European Commission's Horizon Results Booster, Net4Society (or equivalent Horizon Europe National Contact Point Networks), ERA-NETs and Joint Programming Initiatives (JPIs) on Climate, European Climate Research Alliance (ECRA), Joint Programming Initiative Climate (JPI Climate), European Topic Centre on Climate Change Adaptation (ETC CA), European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities (ALLEA)/ Science Advice for Policy by European Academies (SAPEA), European Regions Research and Innovation Network (ERRIN).</p>
<p>Exploitation pathway</p>	<p>Direct interaction (face-to-face) with stakeholders, and through online meetings.</p>

KER12	
<p>© Adaptation AGORA</p>	<p>Adaptation AGORA online presence. The Adaptation AGORA social media channels, the institutional website, the Zenodo community, the hosting on weADAPT and Dataclime, and the journals, are guaranteeing the exploitation of the results online.</p>
<p>Main contributors to the KER</p>	<p>All partners.</p>
<p>IP background</p>	<p>No IP background for KERs identified</p>
<p>KER owner</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Expected benefits from exploiting the KER</p>	<p>Inspiring the creation of new projects, collaborations, and activities. An online presence is crucial for projects of this kind. The social media platforms and the institutional website provide a cost-effective way to reach a large audience and build a community around the project, attracting potential stakeholders, sharing results and guaranteeing their exploitation. The social media channels and the institutional website contributed to the fact that new Followers requested to join the project, and that the Adaptation AGORA “voice” spread in many different countries even outside Europe. Moreover, the Zenodo community and other repositories (such as peer-reviewed journals) are allowing Adaptation AGORA to share outputs such as mapping, protocols, and databases, expanding the exploitation opportunities of the project.</p>
<p>Target groups</p>	<p>All groups.</p>
<p>Specific EU organisations that could benefit from the KER</p>	<p>European Citizen Science Association (ECSA), European Environmental Bureau (EEB), European Youth Forum (YFJ), Pan-European Educational Networks, National Youth Climate Networks, Future Earth, International Centre for Climate Change and Development (ICCCAD), Climate Change High-Level Champions (UNFCCC), C40 Cities Climate Leadership Group.</p>
<p>Exploitation pathway</p>	<p>Promoting the online channels and platforms, considering the possibility to link them to other projects and initiatives also in the future, such as to a potential continuation of Adaptation AGORA.</p>

To ensure the long-term visibility and potential uptake of key project outcomes, selected KERs are being submitted to the [Horizon Results Platform](#) during the project closure phase which spans until March 2026. This platform will guarantee the visibility and possible exploitation of Adaptation AGORA results to a wide audience. The initial selection of KERs for submission took place during the project's lifetime, and the consortium will continue to submit relevant results if opportunities arise, even after the project concludes. Adaptation AGORA leveraged the Platform's dedicated feature for policy influence by submitting its policy white paper to the session targeting results aimed at shaping policy. This strategy ensures our findings remain accessible to policymakers and stakeholders across the European research and innovation ecosystem.

7. Current evidence from the direct exploitation of Adaptation AGORA results

While Adaptation AGORA finishes in December 2025, many of the outputs that were generated throughout the lifetime of the project were highly valuable for decision-makers, scientists and other target audiences. The development of the citizen engagement initiatives mapping; the execution of the activities in the Pilot regions, creating protocols for focus groups, inception and final workshops; and carrying out interviews and surveys with experts; were all of high interest to be incorporated into Horizon Europe projects

One of the first projects that started implementing the results obtained in Adaptation AGORA was the Horizon Europe SCIENCEUS project, which focuses on selecting key citizen engagement initiatives and helping upscale their outreach efforts. In doing so, the project provides these initiatives with various tools, among which are the citizen engagement protocols (including workshops, focus groups and surveys) [created within Adaptation AGORA](#), as well as the ICTs. In this case, these projects funded through SCIENCEUS will gain knowledge and be able to exploit the academies, apps, and other outputs in their own local citizen engagement initiatives.

The Horizon Europe project [TICCA4DANU](#) which was launched in mid 2024 incorporates the implementation of citizen-engagement methodologies developed in Adaptation AGORA as well as using the ICTs also created in this project. As the project focuses on the adaptation to climate change risks in the Danube Macro-Region, the experiences from the various pilots carried out in Adaptation AGORA, together with the various positive deviations where specific stakeholders were involved, provide valuable insights, methodologies and tools for a large number of target audiences. The same is true for the Horizon Europe TRIGGER project where five Climate Health Connection labs (CHC Labs) have been established to improve heatwave risk management. Adaptation AGORA work in the pilots with socially vulnerable groups has been inspirational for the development of the CHC Lab in Geneva, Switzerland.

Another Horizon Europe initiative that was launched in February 2025, [LIQUIDICE](#), which focuses on studying the impact of climate change on snow and ice in vulnerable areas. By using satellite data

and ground observations, the project improves models and helps predict future changes. It also aims to inform strategies for managing water resources, hydropower and adapting to climate challenges. Here the results from Adaptation AGORA will be used as a baseline in terms of existing policies, interaction with stakeholders and how to empower citizens and bring knowledge to target audiences integrated in the strategies proposed.

Also, in 2025 the Horizon Europe SystR project was launched, which will propose a groundbreaking approach to improve the existing science-policy nexus with innovative solutions to address systemic risks, incorporating Smart Specialization Strategies. The project focuses on three contexts in France, Slovakia and Italy, in this last case being Rome the metropolitan area chosen, expanding on the experiences carried out through Adaptation AGORA where this same city was one of the Pilots.

The citizen engagement methodologies implemented in the Pilots, together with the ICTs developed to expand knowledge-acquisition and empower individuals will be tested and used in SystR. Likewise, as the project focuses on the science-policy nexus, the results from the Adaptation AGORA Policy whitepaper and policy analysis, together with the capacity building initiatives, will also serve as a baseline in this new project.

The exploitation of Adaptation AGORA results will not only be visible in Horizon Europe projects, but also in other initiatives, as it is the case of the [bePrepARed](#) Interreg Project between Italy and Croatia.

Additionally, the positive results from the Pilots carried out in the Adaptation AGORA project created further collaborations. One example is the case of the [Rome Climate Change Adaptation: Monitoraggio e Strumenti per l'Adattamento](#) which is a spin-off from the Rome Pilot. In this case, the Pilot leader, CMCC, will provide support to Roma Capitale co-developing research tools that can support the local government in tackling the challenge of climate change adaptation. Another example is the case of City of Malmö and the HeatSafe project that will continue to explore vulnerability and adaptation to heatwaves, supporting Malmö's efforts to make the city more resilient heat stress. The project is a collaboration between SEI HQ, City of Malmö, Linköping University and Basque Centre for Climate Change (BC3).

However, the positive outcomes did not only increase the willingness from the Pilot regions, they also gathered the attention from followers and other regions in Europe who wished to replicate, implement and adapt some of the activities carried out within the Adaptation AGORA project. Such is the case of SRACC-Camp Adapt, supporting the Campania Region in southern Italy in designing and implementing their climate change adaptation strategy. In this case the partnership between the local government and CMCC will allow the Rome Pilot leader to implement awareness-raising activities, promoting the development of communication and inclusion of key stakeholders by using the protocols and methodologies developed in various projects, including Adaptation AGORA.

These examples show how the communication and dissemination plan has been effectively implemented since the early stages of the project. This allowed the creation of synergies with other

institutions as well as increasing the brand awareness of Adaptation AGORA and reputation of the project. This generated a ripple effect in stakeholders from all target audiences wishing to learn more about the results of the project, evaluating how they could be implemented in their knowledge areas and/or regions.

8. Conclusions

Exploitation activities focused on two main goals: securing the long-term sustainability of the project's most valuable assets and formally integrating project results into existing political agendas through targeted event promotion. The Pilot activities and co-creation events acted as the vital starting point for this exploitation, generating the first validated outputs and proof-of-concept solutions that became the foundation for all subsequent outreach.

This validated approach was then amplified through high-level international forums, such as the presence at COP30 (Belém, Brazil), which was dedicated on the one hand, to showcasing the overall project framework and the Digital Tools directly to international decision-makers; and on the other hand, to moderate a workshop on misinformation hosted by the Spanish Pavillion. This shows the level of exposure and validation of the project results, together with the potential exploitation of the outputs and expertise by decision makers all over the world.

Being selected as moderators for a panel in this international framework confirms the reputation the project generated throughout the lifecycle. This strategy opened pathways for global replication and policy alignment based directly on the validated outputs of the four pilot activities. For regional institutional uptake, focused events such as the Baltic Sea Regional Forum (Estonia) and the Regional Expert Workshop (Romania) targeted EU regions, cities, and policy-makers to share the co-production methodologies and pilot results with peers who were best positioned to formally integrate these practices into regional adaptation and investment planning.

In parallel, business and industry engagement was essential. Specific events, such as the Malmö property owner event, were organized to build awareness and interest in heat-risk solutions among property owners, facilitating future market uptake and collaborative urban planning initiatives necessary for large-scale solution deployment. Other examples include co-hosting webinars with multinational firms, increasing the level of interest from the private sector in the results from our project and how they could benefit from incorporating such variables in business models, rendering their strategic approach more sustainable.

Project legacy planning efforts remained focused on the further integration of the KERs and the associated future exploitation. This process was continually updated to ensure the legal and technical frameworks were in place for the long-term digital sustainability and legacy of core assets like the ACH and digital handbook after the project's completion. Those products will benefit from long lasting hosting provided respectively by the weADAPT platform and by the Dataclime platform.

The Adaptation AGORA legacy, in its various forms, will also be available on the website and on the social media channels for other 5 years after the end of the project. Archiving of project data and methodologies in open repositories like Zenodo, the Horizon Results Platform, and the European Citizen Science platform will guarantee an accessible and enduring legacy for the project's knowledge base. The strategic sequencing and grouping of these activities guaranteed that the Adaptation AGORA project successfully leveraged its communications and dissemination output to facilitate its exploitation goals.

By targeting policymakers with concrete institutionalization pathways and scalable tools, the project provided the necessary instruments to achieve actual, long-term transformational changes. Examples include the herein described [Rome Climate Change Adaptation: *Monitoraggio e Strumenti per l'Adattamento*](#), which continues expanding on the legacy from this project's experiences in citizen engagement.

Lastly, the exploitation strategy includes a set of activities incorporated in the Communication and Dissemination Plan (D6.4) that will be conducted after the project end, this is for example the case of the Adaptation AGORA participation at the [Stockholm smart city expo 2026](#) that will take place in Stockholm in May 2026, and that will focus on the Malmö case study, or participating at EGU 2026.

